

THE MOTIVATION AND QUALITIES TO LEAD: A STUDY ON CSUF STUDENT LEADERS

by

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Abstract

On a campus of 40,000 students, Cal State Fullerton has many clubs and organizations on campus in which student leadership plays an integral role in day-to-day activities in these organizations. For my Senior Honors Project, I wanted to study why students at CSUF take on the role of student leaders and what qualities they believe makes an effective student leader on campus. This study discusses how the student leaders that were surveyed partake in student leader positions because of financial compensation, resume building, making friends, and networking. Additionally, the top qualities that the student leaders believe makes an effective leader are empathy, resourcefulness, confidence, ambition, and optimism. Student leadership is crucial in order to cultivate a community on campus and a sense of belonging. With this project I wanted to highlight the hard work and efforts that student leaders do because they are the backbone of our Cal State Fullerton community.

Introduction

Students across college campuses are strongly encouraged to join different student organizations on campus ranging from student government, fraternity and sororities, residence halls, and professional major-related clubs in order to grow their leadership skills and increase their marketability in the professional world. Studies have shown that students who are involved in extracurricular activities tend to have better grades and lower drop-out rates than the students who are not involved in on-campus organizations ¹. The success and attractiveness of these on-campus organizations relies heavily on how the organization is run, this is where student leadership plays a pivotal role. With strong leadership, there is higher retention, participation, and community ². Leadership can be something that may feel daunting to some students, the word “leader” or “leadership” is a very broad term that can have a different meaning to students, “there are almost as many different definitions of leadership as there are persons who have attempted to define the concept” ³. People’s perceptions of leadership vary from one person to another and there are no guidelines to follow in order to become a successful leader. In addition to varying leadership perceptions, it is important to note that college students come from different backgrounds, with some students having more access to resources and opportunities than others which may reflect on one group of students being involved in leadership positions more than others (for example first-gen students, students that have jobs, etc). With this study, I

¹ Positive Effects of Extra Curricular Activities on Students. <https://dc.cod.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1370&context=essai>.

² “Why Student Leadership Is Important in Education?” Bishop Tyrrell Anglican College, 12 Jan 2022, <https://www.btac.nsw.edu.au/news/test-article#:~:text=It's%20important%20for%20students%20to,effective%20communication%20and%20interpersonal%20skills>.

³ Bass, Bernard M., and Ralph M. Stogdill. Handbook of Leadership: A Survey of Theory and Research. Free Press, 1981.

wanted to focus on student leaders at California State University, Fullerton and how they view leadership. Since there are many definitions on what a leader is, I wanted to focus on what students believe is the top quality of being a student leader. The survey that will later be discussed focuses on what are the top qualities student leaders believe make an effective leader and what are the main motivations as to why students take leadership positions on campus.

Background on CSUF

California State University, Fullerton is located in Orange County, California. The university has a population size of about 41,000 students with over 300 clubs and organizations that cover many different interests and needs, including social, cultural, academic, sport, faith, and community service⁴. This university is the largest university in the 23-campus CSU system with the demographic of the student body consisting of 46% Hispanic or Latino students, 20.6% Asian students, 18.7% White students, and 2.09% Black students⁵. California State University, Fullerton is widely considered as a commuter campus, with many students opting to drive their car or take the bus to campus rather than dorming. Because of so many students commuting on campus, student leadership plays a vital role in ensuring that students stay involved in campus life. With great leadership students are able to stay involved on campus and the overall experience of students at CSUF is enhanced.

Problem Statement

⁴ "Clubs & Organizations - Student Life and Leadership: CSUF." Cal State Fullerton, <http://www.fullerton.edu/sll/involvement/clubs/>.

⁵ "California State University-Fullerton." *Data USA*, <https://datausa.io/profile/university/california-state-university-fullerton#:~:text=The%20enrolled%20student%20population%20at%20California%20State%20University%2DFullerton%20is,American%20Indian%20or%20Alaska%20Native.>

According to the Oxford Dictionary, it states that the word “leadership” is defined as “the action of leading a group of people or an organization”⁶. The problem with defining leadership is that this term is very broad because there are many definitions of leadership. In academia, this term is highly debated due to the nature of how leadership is expressed and thought by others, there are many styles, many paths to effective leadership⁷. There are no set of rules or steps in becoming an effective leader, everyone has their own style of leadership which brings the question as to what are the top qualities in being a leader and why do people want to lead? According to the Harvard Business Review, they interviewed top CEOs of various companies to see what were the top qualities of a leader and found that empathy, confidence, goal-oriented, ambition, and optimism were the top qualities that CEOs find is important to have in a leader⁸. Furthermore, leadership positions provide the opportunity for students to reach personal goals, to build their resume, to receive a scholarship for being in a leadership position, and to network with other students. In the survey I sent to students, I asked them what they believe is the most important quality of being a leader according to the qualities mentioned by The Harvard Business Review and what was the main reason as to why they decided to take the leadership position they are in. Additionally, I asked students what is the best part of being a student leader and what was the hardest part about being a student leader.

⁶ “Leadership Noun - Definition, Pictures, Pronunciation and Usage Notes: Oxford Advanced American Dictionary at Oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com.” Leadership Noun - Definition, Pictures, Pronunciation and Usage Notes | Oxford Advanced American Dictionary at OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com, https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/us/definition/american_english/leadership.

⁷ Juntrasook, Adisorn. “‘You Do Not Have to Be the Boss to Be a Leader’: Contested Meanings of Leadership in Higher Education.” Higher Education Research & Development, vol. 33, no. 1, 2014, pp. 19–31., <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2013.864610>.

⁸ “Understanding Leadership.” Harvard Business Review, <https://hbr.org/2004/01/understanding-leadership>.

Method Of Study

After IRB approval, (IRB: HSR-21-22-291) I conducted a survey specifically for student leaders to ask them the questions referenced above. For my survey, I used Google Forms to ask the questions and all responses were answered online via the form. In order to get a good sample, I incentivized my survey by offering 4 \$5 Starbucks gift cards to be raffled for students that take my survey. In total 52 student leaders took my survey that represented various clubs and organizations on campus ranging from cultural organizations, major-related clubs, Greek life organizations, ASI leaders, RA's.

Survey Questions

1. Age

2. Gender

* Male

* Female

* Non-binary

* Other

* Prefer not to state

3. Are you a first-gen student?

* Yes

* No

4. What club or organization on campus are you involved in?

5. What is the main reason behind joining a leadership position?

* Financial compensation

* Resume building

* Personal growth

* Networking

* Other (please state)

6. Of the qualities below, which do you believe is the most important quality to have in order to be an effective student leader?

* Empathy

* Confidence

* Goal-oriented

* Ambition

* Optimism

7. In your opinion, what is the hardest thing about being a leader?

8. In your opinion, what is the best thing about being a leader?

Data

Question: Of the qualities below, which do you believe is the most important quality to have in order to be an effective student leader?

Figure 1

Of the 52 students surveyed, 44.5% selected empathy as the most important quality of a leader followed by confidence at 28.8%, goal-oriented at 11.5%, lastly ambition and optimism both tied at 7.6%. From these results it can be concluded that student leaders at California State University, Fullerton find that being empathetic is an important quality in being an effective student leader. Students value a leader that is able to connect with students and understand others' different perspectives. With such a big campus like California State University, Fullerton with many students there are many wants and needs so student leaders need to actively listen to

students and try their best to listen to their many needs in order for them to have an inclusive experience.

Question: What is the main reason behind joining a leadership position?

Figure 2

Of the 52 student leaders surveyed, 42.3% selected personal growth as the main reason why they chose to become a student leader on campus. 34.6% of students selected resume building and 23.1% of students selected networking for the reasons why they selected to become a student leader. It's important to note that no student selected financial compensation as the primary reason why they chose to become a student leader on campus. With these results students at California State University, Fullerton decided to join leadership positions because of personal growth, many students step into these leadership positions to learn different skills and learn more about their own abilities.

Additional Findings from Survey

Question: What is the best part about being a student leader?

From this question, many student leaders expressed that they love to make an impact on students. The most common answer was that they felt a rewarding feeling helping other students and leading other students to be successful at California State University, Fullerton. Through their guidance and mentorship they have been able to change the lives of students and create lasting experiences with the students they work and interact with. Furthermore, student leaders also expressed how much they really enjoyed collaborating with other students in their clubs and organizations to plan events and meetings. Many students expressed that they made many friendships through collaboration but they also learned new skills such as teamwork and time management with the responsibilities of their roles.

Question: What is the hardest part about being a student leader?

From this question, student leaders expressed that balancing school was very difficult for them because of all the responsibilities they had to juggle. Additionally, some students expressed that they felt a lot of pressure from their positions because of how many students depended on them and did not want to fail. There were also many responses regarding mental health where students stated that sometimes they forget to take care of themselves because they are so focused on helping others. The big responsibilities they have on the daily have taken a mental toll on students because of the pressure or expectations to be exceptional at their job. Students also stated how sometimes it can be tiring to always be the one making important decisions all the

time, but they do not want to let down their club, organization, or other students that are depending on them to achieve the goals of the organization.

Conclusion

With the results from the survey, it can be concluded that student leaders at California State University, Fullerton highly value empathy in order to become a successful leader on campus. With a big campus of 40,000 students, it is crucial for student leaders to listen to the many different perspectives that are on campus in order to connect with other students. An empathetic leader is able to problem solve and ensure that student voices are heard in order for students to feel comfortable in their community. The findings from the survey also suggest that many students take on leadership positions on campus for personal growth. Many students stated that they wanted to step out of their comfort zone and take risks by taking on a big responsibility of leading other students. With these positions that they have taken they have expressed that they learned more about themselves as a leader and developed new skills and attributes that they will take on with them in their professional careers when they finish college. Additionally, mental health should be taken into account for student leaders and they need more support so that they can take care of themselves. Many students expressed that they were struggling with pressure, expectations, and burnout due to their roles so it is crucial that students get support from the university to ensure that they are utilizing services such as CAPS to take care of their mental health. Student leaders play a pivotal role at California State University, Fullerton because they help to enhance the Titan Experience on campus. They are an important asset because of their roles of ensuring the success of their clubs and organizations, they also provide guidance and

mentorship to students which greatly impacts their college experience at California State University, Fullerton.

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